

MICROCRACKING IN LAYERS OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES IN CYCLIC LOADING WITH TENSILE TRANSVERSE STRESS COMPONENT IN LAYERS

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ABSTRACT

Intralaminar cracking in layers of a quasi-isotropic carbon fiber NCF laminate in tension-tension cyclic loading is studied experimentally. Methodology based on modified Weibull analysis is suggested to combine quasi-static and fatigue testing to identify parameters in the crack density growth model. The validity of the assumptions for the given material is experimentally confirmed. The suggested methodology can lead to significant time and material savings in composites fatigue behaviour characterization.

1 INTRODUCTION

Structural elements made of composites usually contain laminates consisting of several layers with fibre orientations optimized with respect to applied loads. Several microdamage modes appear in layers before the final macroscopic failure of the composite laminate. Due to microdamage the thermo-elastic constants of the laminate are reduced. The transverse tensile strain to failure is the lowest among the failure strain components of unidirectional (UD) composites and the first observed damage mode is intralaminar cracking of layers with off-axis orientation with respect to the main load direction. Cracks are initiated as a result of action of transverse tensile stress [1] with shear stress contribution.

Intralaminar cracks run parallel to the fiber direction in the layer not breaking fibres and the crack plane is perpendicular to the laminate middle-plane (x-y plane in Fig. 1). Usually in tensile tests these cracks cover the whole thickness of the layer and propagate over the whole width of the specimen. Since the number of cracks increases during service life, they may significantly impair the effective properties of the laminate [2]. They also initiate other damage modes, such as local delamination at the intralaminar crack tip [3], and fibre breaks in neighbouring plies.

The severity of intralaminar damage in layer is quantified with crack density which is defined as number of cracks in a layer over certain distance. The crack density in k-th layer is denoted ρ_k (cracks/mm). Average distance between cracks, which is inverse to the crack density, is $2l_k = 1/\rho_k$. In a region of very high crack density, often called saturation region the spacing between cracks is approximately equal to t_k .

Two major stages can be recognized in development of each intralaminar crack: initiation and propagation. Whereas the initiation is often considered as independent on geometrical parameters allowing using approaches with “in situ” strength, the propagation (growth of the tunnel along fibres) is analysed using linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) using concept of released potential energy.

The objective of this paper is to present and to validate methodology for intralaminar cracking analysis in tension –tension fatigue for laminates with relatively thick damaged layers. The considered example is quasi-isotropic CF/EP NCF laminate.

Figure 1: Schematic showing of the upper part of symmetric laminate with cracks in different layers

2 MECHANICS OF CRACK INITIATION AND GROWTH

If the far-field transverse stress in the layer of the undamaged layer is tensile, each crack has two traction free surfaces and the in-plane stresses on the crack surface are zero. With increasing distance from the crack the transverse stresses and the in-plane shear stresses recover and they may asymptotically approach the far-field values. The stress transfer from the undamaged layer to the damaged is accompanied by high out-of-plane shear stresses at the layer interface in the vicinity of the crack. The described stress recovery mechanism allows creating many cracks in the same layer with increasing external load.

The two phases in development of each individual crack discussed in this paper are : a) initiation and b) propagation (growth) mostly due to the tensile transverse stresses in the layer. Large in-plane shear stresses (if present) would contribute to crack initiation and propagation. Still, the crack opening mode (Mode I) is the dominant mode on all scales. In this paper the methodology is described for case with transverse stresses only. However, it does not affect the generality of the approach and mixed mode criteria can be easily implemented instead.

The definition of the initiation and propagation of the crack is rather diffuse. The crack initiation is a process on fiber/resin scale (microscale) which leads to development of a mesoscale damage entity (defect, flaw....). Detailed analysis of initiation is very complex and it is outside the scope of this paper. Generally speaking the sequence of micro-events is known: dependent on interface properties it is a combination of failure of interface leading to prolonged debonds and/or resin failure followed by coalescence of these small damage entities into larger damage entity which after reaching critical size grows unstable in the layer thickness direction. This growth is arrested when the crack approaches the interface with the neighbouring layer.

Since reliable micromechanics analysis for evaluating the necessary applied strain or stress level for crack initiation is not available, we are using a pragmatic approach stating that the initiation stress, σ_{in} is a material system dependent stress level required to initiate a defect large enough to grow unstably in thickness direction. We assume that the initiation stress level does not depend on the thickness of the layer. For very thin layers with thickness of about 5-7 fibre diameters we can expect a slight increase of the initiation stress for thin layers because in laminate the layer boundaries with almost uniform strain condition are too close to the local fibre/matrix cell and periodic conditions are not valid anymore. Even without the above effects the initiation stress σ_{in} in transverse loading is

expected to be higher than the transverse tensile strength of the same unidirectional (UD) composite, σ_T^+ .

When it is energetically possible the initiated crack propagates also along the fiber direction creating a tunnel in the layer. The propagation is usually analysed ignoring the fibre/matrix microstructure and considering the layer in the laminate as a homogeneous material. According to LEFM the available potential energy has to be equal or larger than the work required creating a new crack surface. The above expressed in terms of LEFM for Mode I growth states: the strain energy release rate has to be equal or larger than its critical value G_{IC} .

The energy release rate in Mode I is proportional to the square of the in-plane transverse stress in the layer in the location of cracking. It is also proportional to the cracked layer thickness. From here and the propagation criterion the stress level σ_{prop} for crack propagation σ_{prop} has $1/\sqrt{t_k}$ dependence on ply thickness t_k . Two scenarios can describe what follows after initiation, See Fig.2.

If the stress level necessary to initiate the crack is high and the layer is thick

$$\sigma_{in} > \sigma_{prop} \quad (1)$$

In this case the crack after initiation will propagate in an unstable manner. In terms of released energy it means that at the initiation stress level the available energy release rate is higher than the critical value. In this case the initiation stress governs the multiple cracking process and fracture mechanics is not applicable tool for multiple cracking analysis.

Another possibility is that the stress for the initiation, σ_{in} is rather low and/or the ply is very thin resulting in

$$\sigma_{in} < \sigma_{prop} \quad (2)$$

After initiation the crack will not propagate: the available energy release rate for crack propagation is lower than the critical value. Nothing will happen directly after the initiation and higher stress has to be applied to get this crack propagating and the cracking is propagation governed.

Figure 2: Schematic showing of transverse stress for initiation and propagation dependence on layer thickness

According to described scenario, in thin layer crack may be initiated at roughly the same stress as in thick layers but its propagation is delayed. Unfortunately, the thickness of the layer at which transition takes place from the initiation stress σ_{in} controlled cracking behaviour to ply thickness dependent propagation stress σ_{prop} controlled behaviour depends on the composite system used and has to be determined in tests.

3 STATISTICAL NATURE OF INITIATION STRESS DISTRIBUTION

The above discussion does not explain why at certain load level only one crack appears and the next crack is created only if the load is increased. In several locations fibers are very close to each other or even touching. These locations are randomly distributed in the specimen and there: a) the stress concentrations are higher than in a unit cell with average fibre content; b) due to limited space between fibres impregnation with resin may be imperfect, leading to reduced interface and resin failure properties.

Consequently the reason for continuous increase of crack density with applied load is the statistical nature of failure properties distribution in the layer. The failure properties are not the same in all locations along the transverse direction of the layer: there are some weaker positions where the first cracks occur and more strong positions requiring larger applied load. There is an evidence that the transverse strength (initiation stress) obeys Weibull distribution [4,5,6]. The cracking rate increases with applied load because stress levels are reached where the material has the highest probability density of failure and many positions have similar failure properties. After that the cracking slows down because the probability density approaches to zero. Hence, the horizontal line for initiation stress in Fig.2 should be replaced by a horizontal band with the horizontal line representing the average value of initiation stress (strength).

Another phenomenon slowing down the cracking rate in the high crack density region is the stress state between cracks. There is no enough distance between cracks for stress recovery and the maximum values of the in-plane stresses between two cracks is lower than the far-field value. Therefore creation of a new crack requires significantly higher applied load.

Assessing the multiple cracking phenomenon each layer where cracks may be expected is considered as consisting of many small elements in its in-plane transverse direction. Each element has its individual intralaminar cracking initiation stress. Weibull strength distribution is assumed to describe the variation in σ_{in} between elements but the geometrical position of element with a given σ_{in} is random. The initiation stress σ_{in} distribution is in the form

$$P_{in} = 1 - \exp \left[-\frac{V}{V_0} \left(\frac{\sigma_T}{\sigma_{ino}} \right)^m \right] \quad (3)$$

In (3) P_{in} is the probability that crack is initiated when the transverse tensile stress in the element is σ_T ; m and σ_{ino} are the shape and the scale parameters obtained in tests with reference specimens of element volume V_0 ; V is the volume of the considered element.

In the simple approach presented below the length of the element in the transverse direction is related to the maximum possible crack density and is selected so that each element may crack not more than once. As a rough estimate based on experimental observations and stress analysis, one can assume that in internal layers at highest crack density the average distance between cracks is approximately equal to the thickness of this layer

$$\rho_{k,max} = 1/t_k \quad (4)$$

According to (4) the number of elements in layer is

$$M = \frac{L}{t_k} = L \cdot \rho_{k,max} \quad (5)$$

The analysis presented in this paper is not a Monte Carlo type of simulation where failure of each individual element is considered explicitly based on local stress distribution between existing cracks and its individual failure properties. In Monte-Carlo simulations each element has to be significantly smaller. Here we express the probability of cracking through crack density without specifying which particular element has failed and ignoring the effect of a crack on stress distribution in other elements ($\sigma_T = \sigma_{T0}$). Index "0" is used for stresses according to CLT. In other words the presented analysis is valid for low crack densities.

The number of cracks at far-field stress in the layer σ_{T0} is related to average spacing, $2l_k$ between them

$$M_{cr} = \frac{L}{2l_k} = L \cdot \rho_k(\sigma_{T0}) \quad (6)$$

The probability of crack initiation at certain stress $P_{in}(\sigma_T)$ can be defined as the number of elements with initiated cracks M_{cr} versus the total number of elements M in the layer

$$P_{in} = \frac{M_{cr}}{M} \quad (7)$$

Substituting (5), (6) in (7) we obtain relationship linking the probability of crack initiation P_{in} with the crack density at certain stress level, σ_{T0} in a layer with index k

$$P_{in}^{(k)} = \frac{\rho_k(\sigma_{T0})}{\rho_{k,max}} \quad (8)$$

To analyse initiation the 90-layer thickness should be in the range where cracking is initiation stress governed: the crack will propagate as soon it is initiated and, hence, the crack is well defined and the number of cracks can be counted on specimen edge. We obtain P_{in}^{90} dependence on transverse stress σ_{T0}^{90} . The stress is calculated using CLT from the applied load (or strain) and from the temperature difference ΔT between manufacturing and testing temperature

$$\sigma_{T0}^{90} = \sigma_{T0}^{90mech} + \sigma_{T0}^{90thermal} \quad (9)$$

Then standard procedure is applied to the obtained experimental probability of failure relationship: we present the data as double logarithm of P_{in}^{90} against $\ln(\sigma_{T0}^{90})$. If the data follow Weibull distribution, the obtained relationship will be linear. Using linear fit to these data we obtain parameters m and σ_{in0} in (3).

More accurate values of Weibull parameters can be found comparing Monte-Carlo simulations with experiment or using the probabilistic approach developed in [6]. Both approaches require analytical models for stress distribution between two cracks applicable for high crack density.

The identified Weibull distribution for crack initiation stress with known parameters m and σ_{in0} can be used to predict the density of initiated cracks, ρ_k in an arbitrary k -th layer of a multidirectional laminate subjected to increasing general thermo-mechanical loading.

4 FATIGUE EFFECT ON INTRALAMINAR CRACK INITIATION

We assume that cyclic loading reduce the resistance of the layer to failure. In terms of Fig. 2 it means that the average transverse stress level for crack initiation is reduced. The statistical transverse initiation stress distribution is changing. To adapt the Weibull distribution to this situation we have to make several assumptions. The main assumption is that the weakest position in the layer regarding crack initiation in quasi-static loading is the weakest position also in cyclic loading. This assumption seems to be justified by the local geometrical origin of the weakest position described above. Following Weibull's derivation of his expression we can assume that the function $n(\sigma)$ characterizing the number of defects per unit volume that at stress σ can develop in cracks depends also on the number of cycles (the defects are growing with the number of cycles). Then the Weibull's assumption that this relationship can be described by a power law can be generalized to

$$n(\sigma_T) = f(N) \left(\frac{\sigma_T}{\sigma_{in0}} \right)^m \quad (10)$$

The simplest form to inspect is a power function

$$n(\sigma_T) = N^\alpha \left(\frac{\sigma_T}{\sigma_{in0}} \right)^m \quad (11)$$

leading to

$$\frac{\rho_k(\sigma_T, N)}{\rho_{k,max}} = 1 - \exp \left[- \frac{V}{V_0} N^\alpha \left(\frac{\sigma_T}{\sigma_{in0}} \right)^m \right] \quad (12)$$

If proven correct this expression would provide a powerful methodology for damage prediction in fatigue. Parameters m and σ_{in0} could be found analyzing multiple cracking in quasi-static loading test whereas $f(N)$ (parameter) could be identified in a limited number of fatigue tests.

5 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Quasi-static tensile loading and cyclic loading with 5 Hz frequency and $R=1$ was conducted on NCF carbon fiber HTS/RTM6 quasi-isotropic laminates with quasi-isotropic $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ lay-up. UD plies consisted of 12K fiber bundles with thickness 0.25mm and width 3.5mm. The damage state in 90-layers of the laminates was characterized using optical microscopy. Typical damage state showing intralaminar cracks in layers as well as delaminations starting from cracks is shown in Fig. 3.

Initiation governed damage development was observed in stepwise quasi-static loading quantifying the damage state after reaching each increasing load/strain level. Typical crack density versus maximum applied strain curve is shown in Fig. 4a.

Figure: 3 Micrograph of intralaminar cracks in layers of quasi-isotropic laminate with bundle mesostructure.

Using these data and the expression (12) at $N=1$ (no fatigue effects) the Weibull analysis of data was performed presenting data in terms of probability of failure in $\ln\text{-}\ln$ axes as shown in Fig. 5. The relationship is really rather linear and from there the two Weibull parameters were determined: $m = 11.28$ and $\sigma_{in0} = 139.5 \text{ MPa}$.

To investigate the N -dependence and the validity of the assumed cycle effect in (12), stress controlled cyclic tests were performed at several maximum initial strain levels. Typical dependence of crack density of number of cycles at 0.5% strain is presented in Fig. 4b. The reached crack density depends on the stress level in the test and the number of cycles.

Taking logarithm of (12) two times we obtain

$$\ln \ln \frac{\rho_{k,max}}{\rho_{k,max} - \rho_k(\sigma_T, N)} = \alpha \ln N + m \ln \frac{\sigma_T}{\sigma_{in0}} + \ln \frac{V}{V_0} \quad (13)$$

According to (13) the relationship between the $\ln \ln ()$ and $\ln N$ is linear and the slope does not depend on the stress level σ_T in the fatigue test.

Increasing stress level would lead to vertical shift of the line. Results presented for in Fig. 6 for cyclic loading data for two strain levels confirm these assumptions: a) the curve is rather linear; b) the slope coefficient α is rather similar at both strain levels (the variation between several specimens in the same loading conditions is even larger than this difference). From Fig. 6 the average values of parameters were calculated: $\alpha = 0.41$ and $\sigma_{in0} = 132 \text{ MPa}$. The σ_{in0} value is slightly lower but similar to the value 139.5 MPa obtained in the quasi-static test. The σ_{in0} value in 0.5% test was 126.2 and in 0.6% test it was 137.5. This result indicates that most probably for this material the fatigue does not reduce the value of σ_{in0} and the assumption (11) can be accepted.

Figure 4: Number of cracks over 50mm distance: a) in quasi-static loading; b) in cyclic loading

Figure 5: Weibull analysis of cracking in 90-layers during quasi-static tensile loading. Obtained parameters are $m = 11.28$ and $\sigma_{in0} = 139.5 \text{ MPa}$

Finally the expression (12) with identified coefficients was used to predict the damage state in specimens subjected to 10^6 cycles at strain 0.2%. Calculations show that there should be 0.065 cracks over 50 mm distance. In performed experiments no cracks were detected. This means that the fatigue threshold (which actually does not exist but in our opinion it is a very low damage probability level) is higher than 0.2% maximum strain.

Figure 6: Cycle dependence of cracking: a) at 0.6% applied strain; b) at 0.5 % applied strain

9 CONCLUSIONS

Methodology is suggested where Weibull probability model of transverse cracking is adjusted for fatigue effects incorporating the dependence of the internal defect state on the number of cycles in form of power law. Part of the parameters in the evolution law can be determined in quasi-static tests. Therefore, only a limited amount of fatigue tests was required for determination of the remaining parameter. The approach is demonstrated on quasi-isotropic NCF composite with cracks in bundles.

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